

The South African National Red List of spiders: patterns, threats, and conservation

Triage in conservation biology necessitates the prioritization of species and ecosystems for conservation. Although highly diverse, ecologically important, and charismatic, spiders are rarely considered.

- With 2,253 known species, South Africa's spider diversity is among the highest in the world. A 22-year initiative culminating in a national assessment of all the South African species saw a 33% increase in described species and a 350% rise in specimen accessions of the national collection annually.
- Endemism is high, at 60% of all South African species. Levels of endemism are particularly high in Fynbos, Succulent Karoo and Forests. Relative to its area, Forests have three times more endemics than any of the other biomes, followed by the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt.
- A total of 127 species (5.7%) are either rare or endangered. Threats to these species are largely linked to habitat destruction in the form of urbanization and agriculture. The bulk (62.8%) of taxa are of least concern, but many species are data deficient (27%).
- Predicted large-scale diversity patterns are confounded by the localized nature of distribution records. Best estimates of compositional turnover point to an east-west bias in our understanding and conservation of spiders in the country, a bias that is most acute in the north-western parts of the country because this region has seen less collecting and has fewer conservation estates.
- In general, rare and threatened species are mainly ground-dwelling taxa that are either relictual or have poor dispersal abilities. Complemented with long term surveys that will provide insights into population dynamics of spiders, exploring the use of species traits in predicting extinction probability could provide additional criteria for conservation prioritization.
- Based on these assessments, targeted species-level interventions might provide a platform for more public awareness and institutional involvement.

FOORD, S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N., SETHUSA, T. & RAIMONDO, D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* **48**: 110–118.

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IUCN Red List of South African spiders included in the Species Environmental Assessment Guideline

Over the last few years, members of the Arachnology unit, under the guidance of Dr Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman, have been working closely with the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) Threatened Species Unit to evaluate all the South African spider species for placement on the IUCN Red List. This project was a massive undertaking, with more than 2200 species individually assessed according to the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria. The ARC and SANBI worked with a number of arachnid specialists from various institutions to evaluate and assess each species according to this international standard. In order to do these assessments, data associated with the National Collection of Arachnida database and the published spider records in the South African National Survey of Arachnida database were used. This data comes from the National Collection of Arachnida, one of the national assets that the ARC-PHP is responsible for.

Based on the assessments of the South African spiders, 3% are considered Threatened, 32% are Data Deficient, 3% are Near Threatened or Rare, and the remaining 62% are considered of Least Concern, meaning they have wider distributions with little or no known threats.

As part of this, South African spider species that are of concern according to the IUCN Categories and Criteria have been included in the Species Environmental Assessment Guideline. This document is the guideline for the implementation of the terrestrial fauna and flora species protocols for environmental impact assessments (EIAs) in South Africa. This means the spider biodiversity in a given area needs to be included in every EIA that is done. This document was produced for the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries by the South African National Biodiversity Institute and BirdLife South Africa.

Furthermore, the spider assessments are also included in the National Screening that is used by EIA practitioners. It is a web-based Environmental Screening Tool that is a geographically-based and web-enabled application that allows a proponent intending to submit an application for environmental authorisation in terms of the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Regulations 2014. This tool is amended to screen their proposed site for any environmental sensitivity. This screening tool can be accessed at <https://screening.environment.gov.za/screeningtool/#/pages/welcome>.

The Screening Tool also provides site- or locality-specific EIA process and review information. For example, the Screening Tool may identify if an industrial development zone, minimum information requirement, Environmental Management Framework or bio-regional plan applies to a specific area.

SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL BIODIVERSITY INSTITUTE (SANBI) 2020. *Species Environmental Assessment Guideline. Guidelines for the implementation of the Terrestrial Fauna and Terrestrial Flora Species Protocols for environmental impact assessments in South Africa.* South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Version 1.2020.

Please contact Robin Lyle at LyleR@arc.agric.za for more information.

A graphic representation of the South African Red List spider species.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

UPDATE OF SOUTH AFRICAN *OLIOS* SPP. (SPARASSIDAE)

JÄGER, P. 2020. The spider genus *Olios* Walckenaer, 1837 (Araneae: Sparassidae) – Part 1: species groups, diagnoses, identification keys, distribution maps and revision of the *argelasius*-, *coenobitus*- and *auricomis*-groups. *Zootaxa* **4866**: 1-119.

In this paper the genus *Olios* Walckenaer, 1837 was partly revised, a generic diagnosis was given, and an identification key was provided to eight species groups. *Olios* in its revised sense includes 87 species and is distributed in Africa, southern Europe and Asia. Previously 23 *Olios* species were known from South Africa, but several changes were proposed by Jäger (2020), such as:

NEW SPECIES

Olios kunzi Jäger, 2020 (Namibia, Zambia, South Africa)

SYNONYMS

Olios aristophanei Lessert, 1936 = *Olios fasciculatus* Simon, 1880

Olios schoenlandi (Pocock, 1900) = *Olios auricomis* (Simon, 1880)

Olios spenceri Pocock, 1896 = *Olios fasciculatus* Simon, 1880

NOMINA DUBIA

Olios derasus (C.L. Koch, 1845) = *Palystes derasus* (C. L. Koch, 1845)

Olios guttipes (Simon, 1897)

Olios maculinotatus Strand, 1909

MISPLACED IN OLIOS, TO BE MOVED TO OTHER GENERA

Olios biarmatus Lessert, 1925

Olios chelifer Lawrence, 1937

Olios chubbi Lessert, 1923

Olios fonticola (Pocock, 1902)

Olios lacticolor Lawrence, 1952

Olios machadoi Lawrence, 1952

Olios marshalli (Pocock, 1898)

Olios stictopus (Pocock, 1898)

VALID OLIOS SPECIES FROM SOUTH AFRICA

Olios auricomis (Simon, 1880)

Olios brachycephalus Lawrence, 1938

Olios correvoni nigrifrons Lawrence, 1928

Olios freyi Lessert, 1929 from D.R. Congo, new to South Africa

Olios kruegeri (Simon, 1897)

Olios provocator Walckenaer, 1837

Olios sherwoodi Lessert, 1929 from D.R. Congo, new to South Africa

Olios sjostedti Lessert, 1921

Olios zulu Simon, 1880

Olios correvoni nigrifrons

Olios auricomis

Araneus holzapfelae Lessert, 1936 now *Hypsosinga holzapfelae* (Lessert, 1936)

Please note that the species *Araneus holzapfelae* was moved by Kioko *et al.* (2021) to the genus *Hypsosinga* as *Hypsosinga holzapfelae*.

KIOKO, G.M., MARUSIK, Y.M., LI, S.Q., KIOKO, E.N. & JI, L.Q. 2021. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of Kenya. *African Invertebrates* **62**: 49-229.

Hypsosinga holzapfelae (Photo: P. Webb).

NEW PUBLICATIONS

BOOYSEN, R. & HADDAD, C.R. 2021. Revision and molecular phylogeny of the spider genus *Micaria* Westring, 1851 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) in the Afrotropical Region. *Zootaxa* **4940**: 1-82.

The genus *Micaria* Westring, 1851 (Araneae, Gnaphosidae) is a group of small (1.85–5 mm) ant-like spiders that can be distinguished from other gnaphosids by their piriform gland spigots that are similar in size to the major ampullate gland spigots. According to the World Spider Catalog, there are 105 species of *Micaria* in the world, of which only three species are known from the African part of the Afrotropical Region, namely *M. chrysis* (Simon, 1910), *M. tersissima* Simon, 1910 and *M. beaufortia* (Tucker, 1923). The objectives of this study were to revise *Micaria* in the Afrotropical Region, providing new and updated records for each of the species, evaluating the relationships between

Micaria beaufortia from Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Photo: P. Webb).

them using COI barcoding data, and providing information on their biology, mimetic relationships and feeding ecology. These objectives were met by collecting fresh material from the KwaZulu-Natal, Western Cape, Northern Cape and Free State provinces in South Africa. Fresh material of *M. tersissima* and *M. chrysis* were collected from their type localities, Kogmaggas and Port Nolloth (Northern Cape Province), respectively, for identification and DNA analyses. COI sequences generated, together with those sourced from Barcode of Life Data Systems (BOLD) and GenBank, were aligned using the ClustalW alignment algorithm in the Mega X software, and molecular phylogenetic analyses were performed using MrBayes for Bayesian Inference (BI) and RaxML for maximum likelihood (ML) analyses. Seventeen new species were described, of which 11 were recorded from South Africa, to go with the three previously described species.

SOUTH AFRICAN SPECIES	DISTRIBUTION
<i>Micaria basaliducta</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	WC
<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	All 9 provinces
<i>Micaria bispicula</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	WC, NC
<i>Micaria chrysis</i> (Simon, 1910)	EC, FC, G, KZN, L, M, NC, WC
<i>Micaria durbana</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	KZN
<i>Micaria felix</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	EC, G, FS, KZN, L, M, NW, WC
<i>Micaria koingnaas</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	NC, WC
<i>Micaria lata</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	NC
<i>Micaria laxa</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	EC
<i>Micaria mediospina</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	EC
<i>Micaria quinque maculosa</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	FS, NC
<i>Micaria sanipass</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	KZN
<i>Micaria scutellata</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	KZN
<i>Micaria tersissima</i> Simon, 1910	NC

NEW PUBLICATIONS

Capobula, a new Afrotropical dark sac spider genus (Trachelidae)

A new Afrotropical genus of the spider family Trachelidae L. Koch, 1872 was described. *Capobula* is represented by five species, known from South Africa and Lesotho only. Adults of both sexes of *Orthobula infima* Simon, 1896, which is widely distributed in the Western Cape, South Africa, were described for the first time, and this species was transferred to *Capobula* as its type species. The species are :

- *C. capensis* Haddad *et al.* 2021 (South Africa: Western Cape)
- *C. neethlingi* Haddad *et al.* 2021 (South Africa: Western Cape)
- *C. montana* Haddad *et al.* 2021 (Lesotho and South Africa: Eastern Cape, Free State and KwaZulu-Natal),
- *C. ukhahlamba* Haddad *et al.* 2021 (South Africa: KwaZulu-Natal)
- *C. infima* (Simon, 1896) (South Africa: Western Cape)

Capobula montana Haddad *et al.* 2021

Capobula infima (Simon, 1896)

HADDAD, C.R., JIN, C., PLATNICK, N.I. & BOOYSEN, R. 2021. *Capobula* gen. nov., a new Afrotropical dark sac spider genus related to *Orthobula* Simon, 1897 (Araneae: Trachelidae). *Zootaxa* **4942**: 41-71.

Afropesa, a new South African spider genus (Entypesidae)

A new mygalomorph spider genus, *Afropesa*, was established for three South African species: the type species, *A. schoutedeni* (Benoit, 1965), was transferred from *Entypesa* Simon, 1902, and two new species were described, *A. gauteng* and *A. schwendingeri*. The new genus differs from other genera of the Entypesidae by a unique set of diagnostic characters, including a flanged embolus and the spermathecae with wide bases and lengthened distal lobes.

- *Afropesa gauteng* Zonstein & Ríos-Tamayo, 2021 (Gauteng)
- *Afropesa schoutedeni* (Benoit, 1965) (Limpopo)
- *Afropesa schwendingeri* Zonstein & Ríos-Tamayo, 2021 (Limpopo)

Afropesa schoutedeni (Benoit, 1965)

ZONSTEIN, S.L. & RÍOS-TAMAYO, D. 2021. *Afropesa*, a new spider genus from South Africa (Araneae: Entypesidae). *Israel Journal of Entomology* **51**: 7-34.

Our trip to KwaZulu-Natal

Ruan Booysen

Organizing fieldtrips can be a pain. It is just admin, admin, and more admin for at least a few weeks. Nevertheless, a fieldtrip along the coast of KwaZulu-Natal was organized to collect *Scytodes* spitting spiders for my PhD research, and I was gladly accompanied by a Spider Club admin and amazing macro photographer, Rudolph Steenkamp, who assisted me and ticked off some of the spiders on his photographer's checklist of Araneae.

Our trip began in early hours of the morning on the 2nd of October 2020 by picking up Rudi and heading off to our first destination, Platberg Nature Reserve, a place I was excited to see. Unfortunately, it was not what we expected. Upon arrival we experienced very unpleasant weather for spider collection, and most of the forest was burned down, leaving behind only naked trees and burned grass covered by a thick fog, a very eerie atmosphere I might add. Fortunately, we did find a few spiders in the trees and in some of the dry leaf litter, of which the majority were heckled mesh-web spiders (Phyxelididae).

The burned-down forest in the Platberg Nature Reserve on a misty and rainy day.

On the 3rd of October we departed for the uKhahlamba Drakensberg mountains, where we stayed at the ATKV Drakensville Resort. This was a very welcome change of scenery from the flat grasslands of the Free State and much better weather! From here, we had three collection sites, namely the ATKV resort itself, Cathedral Peak (uKhahlamba Drakensberg Park), and the Royal Natal National Park. The Royal Natal National Park yielded us our first batch of *Scytodes* spitting spiders (Scytodidae) from some leaf litter underneath a rock overhang... believe me I was relieved!

Subsequently, we found a bunch of interesting spiders in beating samples, including the recently described "sheep-salti", *Oviballus vidae* (Salticidae).

The recently described *Oviballus vidae*, named after macro photographer and fellow salticid fan, Vida van der Walt.

Sadly, our day at Cathedral Peak was limited to the gate, as the hotel area was off-limits to everyone but guests. However, as entomologists we had no need for fancy dining rooms or bathrooms... we just wanted the bush! We managed to find some more tiny pitch-black *Scytodes* and a few dark sac spiders (Trachelidae) on a hill near the gate. The views from the top were breathtaking to say the least.

The view from the top of the hill next to the Cathedral Peak Gate. I am on the left and Rudi on the right. (Photo: R. Steenkamp).

On the 5th of October we departed for Pietermaritzburg, where we met with Mr Matabaro Ziganira from the KwaZulu-Natal Museum, who we assisted with identifying some unsorted spider material... and yes, there were too many specimens! Our main goal was to extract the *Scytodes* material from the collection. This also gave Rudi an opportunity to also experience the world of spiders via a microscope. Our accommodation here was at the Wensleydale Guest Lodge, a beautiful lodge with a rich diversity of spider and bird life.

During the early mornings, late afternoon, and evenings, we set out to look for some arachnids in their luscious gardens, and surprisingly this place had the highest diversity of spiders we had seen so far. We found a bunch of ant-mimicking jumping spiders (*Myrmarachne* spp., Salticidae), scorpion spiders (*Platyoides leppanae*, Trochanteriidae), various undescribed comb-footed spiders (possibly a *Platnickina* sp. and *Phoroncidia* spp., Theridiidae), and a tailless whip scorpion (*Damon annulatipes*, Amblypygi) to end it all off.

A *Phoroncidia* sp. we found in the garden, trying to hide on a tree stump while still holding her single thread covered in sticky droplets.

After our visit at the museum, we visited Karkloof Canopy Tours on the 8th of October. It was a picture-perfect place, with a dense natural forest, small streams dividing the forest, and tonnes of insects... an entomologist's dream. I am sure by now most of you have heard of the aptly named "strawberry button spider" that had been doing its rounds on the Internet; a blood-red spider with metallic black legs found on Table Mountain. Well, in Karkloof's forest there were millions. We found at least 50 individuals just by beating a few shrubs, and many more walking around on the leaves. These were not the only pretty spiders around, as there were many small neon-green comb-footed spiders (*Meotipa* spp., Theridiidae), jumping spiders (Salticidae), harvestmen (*Rhampsinitus* spp., Phalangiidae, and *Metabiantes* spp., Biantidae) — which smell very sweet — and bark-spiders (*Caerostris* sp., Araneidae). Our goal was to hike up to the top of the hill, but then we realized it was not worth the suffering, and so we turned back.

A rather large male jumping spider, *Thyenula* sp. (Salticidae), from Karkloof Canopy Tours.

A female *Asceua* sp. (Zodariidae) from Vernon Crookes.

You may think: "WOW! Could sampling get any better?", then I would tell you "Yes, yes it can". Our next destination was Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve, a place I will never forget... for good and bad reasons. Let's start with the good, shall we? Starting with the leaf litter just around the office area, we found a rare genus of mainly Asian ant-eating spiders (*Asceua* sp., Zodariidae), and there were hundreds of them running around. This species is undescribed but will get a name in an upcoming study between Arnaud Henrard, Rudy Jocqué and Charles Haddad.

After such a good experience, we dove into the grass tussocks, 100 metres or so further, to see what we can find. Large, cosy tunnels were formed by the hanging grass that contained dozens of different spider taxa, such as tropical wolf spiders (Ctenidae), prowling spiders (*Parapostenus* sp., Miturgidae), spitting spiders, small pholcids (*Quamtana* spp., Pholcidae), and nursery-web spiders (*Euprosthenoopsis* spp., Pisauridae).

The subadult male *Afrarchaea cornuta* that we found in Vernon Crookes. We found a female the following day.

Then it happened, we found it, the spider I have been waiting so long to find... the pelican spider (*Afrarchaea cornuta*, Archaeidae). These incredibly rare spiders are small and slow moving but have extremely elongated chelicerae to catch other spiders with; the fancy word for them would be araneophagic. This was definitely the catch of the day, or even for the trip! However, all good things, as nature would have it, have to be countered with something bad, perhaps a flat tyre the next morning? Not enough, how about breaking the newly replaced front windshield with a low-hanging branch? Yes, that sounds more like it. Very carefully, we drove with the windshield to Richards Bay, where they managed to replace it. Lesson learned.

A beautiful zebra sac spider, *Austraphaea zebra* (Corinnidae) from Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve.

A very tiny female mushroom spider, *Phoroncidia* sp. (Theridiidae) from Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve.

The next destination on our list was Enseleni Nature Reserve, just outside Richards Bay. Unfortunately, we did not have enough time to collect in the reserve due to our car problems, and saw only a glimpse of what it had to offer on the day we arrived. We found a few interesting spiders in a short amount of time in the grass tussocks, including a *Scytodes* sp., *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* (Thomisidae), *Cicynethus subtropicalis* (Zodariidae), and *Panaratella* sp. (Sparassidae). Luckily, the accommodation we stayed at bordered with the natural coastal forest and we could literally just walk out of their backyard into the forest to collect. Thereafter, we drove to St. Lucia to collect in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park, but apparently our permit did not allow us to collect there as we only specified a section of the park, and not the whole park.

Luckily, Clinton Wright, from the Ubuntu Wildlife Trust, had contacted us and asked to come visit them to see the newly described Phinda button spider (*Latrodectus umbukwane*). This seemed very exciting and we opted to go there and do some collecting too. Upon arriving there, Clinton and his wife, Barbara, showed us a female specimen... it was a huge spider, the biggest button I have ever seen! We even tried looking for some in the area but could not find any.

Our last stop was Ndumo Game Reserve. We stayed at Shemula Lodge near the town of Lulwane, and we drove between Ndumo and Tembe Elephant Park to do collecting. We also did some canopy fogging at Ndumo, but it was a bad idea since the wind blew everything off the sheets and I got a chemical burn from sitting in the fogging mixture and Rudi got some in his eyes. Overall, it was a very good trip for collecting *Scytodes*, as we found about 30 individuals and approximately 4-5 species. Rudi, the main photographer of the trip, had taken photos of hundreds of spiders, many of which are new to him and have never been photographed before. In fact, there were so many that we had to take some home to photograph. We had to make use of some of the home appliances to keep the spiders from running away. Nevertheless, it was a fun trip with good company! A trip I would indeed want to go on again!

Rudi and I searching through some of the beats at Clinton and Barbara's house in the Ukuwela Reserve.

Parasmoxidix quadrituberculata (Thomisidae) from Enseleni Nature Reserve.

Nyamiti Pan in the Ndumo Game Reserve, where we spent the whole day collecting and fogging.

SOME INTERESTING FIELD OBSERVATIONS

These interesting colour patterns were observed on *Neoscona* spider specimens received from Namibia (Photos: A. Eichhoff).

With hindsight

Growing up can be a perilous journey, and this little salticid from the Northern Cape is a prime example of this.

Part of the old exoskeleton (exuviae) got stuck on its abdomen during the moulting process. Fortunately, it fell off the next day and the spider has since undergone two more successful moults. It is not mature yet and the genus, species and gender therefore uncertain.

The partially regrown front leg is also now fully healed and perfectly normal.

I felt so sorry for it, but it was also impossible not to laugh at the second little face staring back at me when I was taking photos. It must be a rare occurrence when a failed moult has such a comical result.

P.S. Any doubting Thomases are welcome to contact me for the RAW files.

Contact Vida van der Walt at vidavdw@live.com

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RECENT PUBLICATIONS

BOOYSEN, R. & HADDAD, C.R. 2021. Revision and molecular phylogeny of the spider genus *Micaria* Westring, 1851 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) in the Afrotropical region. *Zootaxa* **4940**: 1–82.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD, S.H., HADDAD, C.R. & LE ROUX, E. 2021. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Augrabies National Park in the Northern Cape Province, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter Supplement* **37**: 16–24.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD, S.H. & HADDAD, C.R. 2021. A list of spider species found in the Marakele National Park, Limpopo Province, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter Supplement* **37**: 9–15.

GALLOWAY, A.D., SEYMOUR, C.L., GAIGHER, R. & PRYKE, J.S. 2021. Organic farming promotes arthropod predators, but this depends on neighbouring patches of natural vegetation. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* **310**: 107295.

GELDENHUYS, M., GAIGHER, R., PRYKE, J.S. & SAMWAYS, M.J. 2021. Diverse herbaceous cover crops promote vineyard arthropod diversity across different management regimes. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* **307**: 107222.

HADDAD, C. R., JIN, C., PLATNICK, N. I. & BOOYSEN, R. 2021. *Capobula* gen. nov., a new Afrotropical dark sac spider genus related to *Orthobula* Simon, 1897 (Araneae: Trachelidae). *Zootaxa* **4942**: 41–71.

HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H. & WHITEHEAD, L. 2021. Tussock parameters, landuse type and drought variably influence spiders associated with *Hyparrhenia hirta* grass tussocks. *African Entomology* **29**: 150–164.

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KIOKO, G.M., MARUSIK, Y.M., LI, S.Q., KIOKO, E.N. & JI, L.Q. (2021). Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of Kenya. *African Invertebrates* **62**: 49–229.

NYFFELER, M. & GIBBONS, J.W. 2021. Spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) feeding on snakes (Reptilia: Squamata). *Journal of Arachnology* **49**: 1–27.

VANUYTVEN, H. 2021. The Theridiidae of the World. A key to the genera with their diagnosis and a study of the body length of all known species. *Newsletter of the Belgian arachnological Society* **35**(Supplement): 1–363.

VAN SCHALKWYK, J., PRYKE, J.S., SAMWAYS, M.J. & GAIGHER, R. 2021. Maintaining high vegetation structural diversity in the landscape promotes arthropod diversity in dynamic production areas. *Landscape Ecology* **36**: 1773–1785.

VISSER, J.H. & GEERTS, S. 2021. Static allometry and sexual dimorphism in the Striped Lesser-thicktail Scorpion *Uroplectes lineatus*. *Arachnology* **18**: 700–707.

VISSER, J.H., GEERTS, S. & JANSEN VAN VUUREN, B. 2021. Phylogeographic patterns in a semi-lithophilous burrowing scorpion, *Opisthophthalmus pallipes*, from South Africa. *Zoological Science* **38**: 36–44.

ZONSTEIN, S. L. & RÍOS-TAMAYO, D. 2021. *Afropesa*, a new spider genus from South Africa (Araneae: Entypesidae). *Israel Journal of Entomology* **51**: 7-34.

IDENTIFICATION GUIDES

The following versions of the South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide have been completed—a total of 2410 pages.

- | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| • AGELENIDAE | • IDIOPIDAE |
| • AMAUROBIDAE | • ISCHNOTHELIDAE |
| • AMMOXENIDAE | • LIOCRANIDAE |
| • ANAPIDAE | • LYCOSIDAE 2 PARTS |
| • ANYPHAENIDAE | • MICROSTIGMATIDAE |
| • ARANEIDAE 3 PARTS | • MIGIDAE |
| • ARCHAEIDAE F | • MIMETIDAE |
| • ATYPIDAE F | • MYSMENIDAE |
| • BARYCHELIDAE | • OECOBIDAE |
| • BEMMERIDAE | • ORSOLOBIDAE |
| • CAPONIIDAE | • OXYOPIIDAE |
| • CHEIRACANTHIIDAE | • PALPIMANIDAE |
| • CITHAERONIIDAE | • PENESTOMIDAE |
| • CLUBIONIDAE | • PHILODROMIDAE |
| • CTENIDAE | • PHYXELIDIDAE |
| • CYATHOLIPIIDAE | • PISAURIDAE |
| • CYRTAUCHENIIDAE | • PYCNOTHELIDAE |
| • DEINOPIIDAE | • SCYTODIDAE |
| • DESIDAE | • SEGESTRIIDAE |
| • DICTYNIDAE | • SELENOPIIDAE |
| • DRYMUSIDAE | • SICARIIDAE |
| • DYSDERIDAE | • SPARASSIDAE |
| • ERESIDAE | • STASIMOPIIDAE |
| • EUAGRIDAE | • TETRAGNATHIDAE |
| • FILISTATIDAE | • THERIDIIDAE 2 PARTS |
| • GALLIENIELLIDAE | • THOMISIDAE 4 PARTS |
| • GNAPHOSIDAE 4 PARTS | • TROCHANTERIIDAE |
| • HAHNIIDAE | • ULOBORIDAE |
| • HERSILIIDAE | |

Anybody looking for these online guides are welcome to contact Ansie at DippenaarA@arc.agric.za. A special thanks to all the photographers sharing their photographs with us. Without them these guides would not have been possible. A special thanks to all who helped with the “crowd editing”, with a special thanks to Astri Leroy for her effort.

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa

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ABSTRACT

An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the Bontebok National Park (BNP) is provided. The checklist was compiled from data collected from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) database. A total of 184 species from 44 families and 134 genera are presently protected in the park. The most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (26 spp.), Salticidae (20 spp.) and Araneidae (19 spp.), while 19 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism and conservation status for each species is provided. Eighty-one of the species have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern. Approximately 8 % of the total South African spider fauna is protected in the Bontebok National Park, and 20 % of the species recorded are South African endemics and 11.4 % are Western Cape endemics. This study provides baseline data on spiders conserved in the Bontebok National Park, which can be used for Red Listing and future assessments of habitat transformation. Only 15 spider species was previously listed from the park and 169 species are newly recorded. Species of special concern are identified, as well as possible new species.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), conservation, endemism, fynbos

INTRODUCTION

As signatories to the Convention on Biodiversity, South Africa is obliged to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable utilization of our species-rich fauna and flora. The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) was initiated in 1997 with the main aim to discover, describe and make an inventory of the South African arachnid fauna. Species distribution data is essential information needed for the conservation assessments to compile a Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa, to have a record of endemic species, and species that are already receiving some protection in existing reserves and parks (McGeoch *et al.* 2011). These species distribution records formed the basis of the first spider atlas and national species list (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010). With continued surveys and new taxonomic data, an updated species list with new information is available.

In South Africa, the Western Cape Province is one of the better sampled provinces, with 966 known species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). However, several areas in the province are still undersampled, and only a few spider checklists of spiders in protected areas have been published: Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2005), Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1999), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). The current study presents the results of data from the SANSa database on the spiders sampled in the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape Province. It includes information on the species' global distribution, endemism and conservation status.

METHODS

Study area and period: Bontebok National Park (BNP) is a species-specific national park in South Africa and was established in 1931 to ensure the preservation of the Bontebok. It is the smallest of South Africa's 20 National Parks and has an extent of 27.86 km². The park is part of the Cape Floristic Region, which is a World Heritage Site. Rebelo *et al.* (2006) classified the vegetation of the BNP as Swellendam Silcrete Fynbos, considering it a poorly known vegetation unit that exhibits floristic features of both fynbos and renosterveld, with very high plant species richness (Fig. 2). The BNP is situated approximately 5 km from the town of Swellendam (Fig. 1) in the Western Cape Province (34°02'S, 20°25'E). The BNP is located in the foothills of the Langeberg Mountains and is bordered to the south by the Breede River. The BNP is situated in the winter rainfall region, and the average annual rainfall is 511 mm, of which 59 % falls in winter.

Sampling methods and identification: Spiders were sampled during short surveys undertaken by the arachnologists of the California Academy of Sciences (October 2011) and the National Museum, Bloemfontein (December 2013). The specimens sampled are housed in their respective collections, but copies of the material sampled was included in the SANSa database. More extensive sampling was undertaken by the last author, who was stationed in the park during 2009 and 2010. Specimens were sampled by hand and preserved in 70% ethanol.

Identifications were done in Pretoria and voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria and the National Museum, Bloemfontein. All this data were used to compile the first checklist of the spiders of BNP (Appendix 1). The taxonomy of certain spider families (e.g. Theridiidae) in southern Africa prevented the identification of some specimens to species level. In some families, only immature specimens were collected and therefore impossible to identify to species level.

FIGURE 1: Map showing location of the Bontebok National Park.

FIGURE 2: Habitat types in the Bontebok National Park (Photos: E. le Roux).

Species endemism and conservation: The conservation status of species is important, and as part of the first edition of the Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010) an endemism index was provided for each species. It was calculated based on current distribution, which included six endemism categories, ranging from: 6 = endemic, known only from type locality / one locality only (Bontebok National Park Endemic, BNPE); 5 = known from one province only, wider than type locality (Western Cape Endemic, WCE); 4 = known from two adjoining provinces only; 3 = South Africa, >two provinces or not adjoining (South African Endemic, SAE); 2 = Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers) (Southern African Endemic, STHE); 1 = Afrotropical Region (African Endemic, AE); 0 = Africa and wider (Cosmopolitan, C).

Regarding conservation status, species that were only recorded from immatures or those that represent possible new species or undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE); species known from only one sex, old material and not revised are data deficient either for taxonomic reasons (DDT) or lack distribution data (DD). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3–5 are South African endemics (SAE), and based on their distribution ranges most of them are also LC. The species in categories 5–6 are Western Cape endemics (WCE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 44 families represented by 134 genera and 184 species have been collected from BNP (Table 3; Appendix 1). In the First Atlas of South African Spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010) only 14 species were listed from BNP. Species were also mentioned in the papers of Schütt (1981) and FitzPatrick (2007). The number of species collected is higher than species recorded from the Karoo National Park, where the 38 families were represented by 116 species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1999), but lower than the De Hoop Nature Reserve, where 252 spp. were sampled after five surveys of between two and 12 days in duration.

In this survey, the Gnaphosidae (26 spp.), Salticidae (20 spp.) and Araneidae (19 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Table 1). There was a very high proportion of singleton families (19), i.e. represented by a single species only.

Species endemism and conservation status: Of the 184 species sampled, 17 spp. (9.2 %) are data deficient (DD), i.e. lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while 10 spp. (5.4 %) were not evaluated (NE), indicating possible new species or species only sampled from juveniles (Table 1; Appendix 1). The majority of the species (153 spp., 83.2 %) sampled are listed as being of least concern (LC), 49 species are Africa endemics, while 46 spp. (25 %) are endemic to southern Africa.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Bontebok National Park, with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S) sampled.

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	2	2	Mimetidae	1	1
Amaurobiidae	2	2	Oecobiidae	1	1
Ammoxenidae	1	1	Oxyopidae	1	3
Anapidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	12	19	Philodromidae	3	3
Bemmeridae	2	2	Pholcidae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	2	3	Pisauridae	5	6
Clubionidae	1	3	Salticidae	17	20
Corinnidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	3
Cyrtachenidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	4
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	2	2
Drymusidae	1	1	Sparassidae	3	4
Dysderidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Entypesidae	2	2	Tetragnathidae	2	6
Eresidae	3	3	Theraphosidae	2	3
Gnaphosidae	15	26	Theridiidae	9	13
Hahniidae	1	1	Thomisidae	8	11
Hersiliidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	5	5	Uloboridae	1	1
Liocranidae	1	1	Zodariidae	4	4
Lycosidae	8	13	Zoropsidae	1	1
Migidae	1	1			

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Bontebok National Park.

DISTRIBUTION	SPP.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data deficient (DD)	17	9.2
Not evaluated (NE)	10	5.4
Least concern (LC)	153	83.2
Rare	2	1.1
Near threatened	1	0.6
Vulnerable	1	0.6
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	19	10.3
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	49	26.6
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	46	25
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE)	22	11.9
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	15	8.1
5 – Western Cape endemics (WCE)	21	11.4
6 – Bontebok National Park (BNP)	0	0

TABLE 3: Species of special concern in the Bontebok National Park. Conservation status (STA): DD = data deficient, known from both sexes; DDT = data deficient; LC = Least Concern; RA = Rare; VUL = Vulnerable. Endemism: R = Rare; WCE = Western Cape endemic; NT = Near Threatened.

SPECIES	STA	ENDEMICITY
FAMILY BEMMERIDAE		
<i>Homostola reticulata</i> (Purcell, 1902)	DD	WCE; NT
FAMILY DRYMUSIDAE		
<i>Izithunzi productum</i> (Purcell, 1904)	RA	WCE; R
FAMILY ERESIDAE		
<i>Dresserus collinus</i> Pocock, 1900	DDT	WCE; NT
FAMILY LIOCRANIDAE		
<i>Rhaeboctesis matroosbergensis</i> Tucker, 1920	DD	WCE; NT
FAMILY LYCOSIDAE		
<i>Proevippa lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1903	LC	WCE; R
<i>Pterartoria caldaria</i> Purcell, 1903	DD	WCE; R
<i>Pterartoria polysticta</i> Purcell, 1903	DD	WCE; R
FAMILY MIGIDAE		
<i>Moggridgea terricola</i> Simon, 1903	VUL	under criterion B
FAMILY ENTYPESIDAE		
<i>Hermacha capensis</i> (Ausserer, 1871)	DD	WCE; NT
<i>Lepthercus engelbrechti</i> Ríos-Tamayo & Lyle, 2020	LC	WCE; R
FAMILY SALTICIDAE		
<i>Rumburak bellus</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith 2014	DDT	WCE; R
FAMILY SCYTODIDAE		
<i>Scytodes testudo</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	WCE; NT
FAMILY SELENOPIDAE		
<i>Anyphops lesserti</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	DDT	WCE; R
FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE		
<i>Stasimopus brevipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	DD	WCE; NT
FAMILY THERAPHOSIDAE		
<i>Harpactira cafreriana</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	LC	WCE; NT
<i>Harpactira dictator</i> Purcell, 1902	LC	WCE; NT
<i>Harpactirella domicola</i> Purcell, 1903	DDT	WCE; NT
FAMILY THOMISIDAE		
<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	NT	under criterion B
FAMILY TRACHELIDAE		
<i>Afrocto capensis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	RA	WCE; R
FAMILY ZOROPSIDAE		
<i>Griswoldia robusta</i> (Simon, 1898)	LC	WCE; R

Of the species identified to species level only 58 spp. are South African endemics (Table 1; Appendix 1). There are presently no endemic species known from the BNP, but 22 species from 16 families are Western Cape endemics (SAE-WCE). These species are of special concern due to their small distribution ranges, and more sampling is needed to resolve this. For other species, many need redescriptions or descriptions of the opposite sex (Table 2).

Preliminary investigations into the biodiversity of the invertebrate fauna in South Africa have highlighted the dilemma caused by a lack of baseline information on the ecology and diversity of most arachnid groups (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002). With the ecology and diversity of the spider fauna of South Africa so poorly known, each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species.

CONCLUSION

As signatories to the Convention on Biological Diversity, South Africa is obliged to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable utilization of the diverse and species rich fauna and flora. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. Established parks, such as BNP, can make a substantial contribution towards invertebrate conservation. However, the contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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FIGURE 3: Selected spiders from the Bontebok National Park. (A) *Harpactira cafreriana* (Walckenaer, 1837) (Theraphosidae); (B) *Harpactira dictator* Purcell, 1902 (Theraphosidae); (C) *Harpactirella domicola* Purcell, 1903 (Theraphosidae); (D) *Palystes castaneus* (Latreille, 1819) (Sparassidae); (E) *Anyphops capensis* (Lawrence, 1940) (Selenopidae); (F) *Evippomma squamulatum* (Lycosidae); (G) *Argiope trifasciata* (Forsskål, 1775) (Araneidae); (H) *Simorcus haddadi* Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010 (Thomisidae) (Photos: E. le Roux).

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Bontebok National Park, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution (DIST). * indicates species previously recorded from the park.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
AGELENIDAE	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Pseudauximus pallidus</i> Purcell, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Chresiona</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
AMMOXENIDAE	<i>Ammoxenus pentheri</i> Simon, 1896	2	LC	STHE
ANAPIDAE	<i>Crozetulus rhodesiensis</i> Brignoli, 1981*	2	LC	STHE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Argiope aurocincta</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C
	<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa elongatus</i> (Lawrence, 1947)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C. L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinioides</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C. L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE
	BEMMERIDAE	<i>Homostola reticulata</i> (Purcell, 1902)	5	DD
<i>Spiroctenus validus</i> (Purcell, 1902)		5	DD	SAE
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona ansiae</i> Lotz, 2002*	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona krugerensis</i> Lotz, 2003	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona lawrencei</i> Roewer, 1951	2	LC	STHE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypha</i> sp. (new)		NE	
DICTYINIDAE	<i>Archaeodictyna</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
DRYMUSIDAE	<i>Izithunzi productum</i> (Purcell, 1904)	5	RARE	SAE
DYSDERIDAE	<i>Dysdera crocata</i> C.L. Koch, 1838	0	LC	C
ENTYPESIDAE	<i>Hermacha capensis</i> (Ausserer, 1871)	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Lepthercus engelbrechti</i> Ríos-Tamayo & Lyle, 2020	5	LC	SAE
ERESIDAE	<i>Dresserus collinus</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Aphantaulax stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina pavesii</i> (Simon, 1897)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina procurva</i> (Purcell, 1908)	1	LC	STHE

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leptodrassex</i> sp. (new)		NE	
	<i>Megamyrmaekion schreineri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Poecilochroa involuta</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Prodidomus capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pterotricha auris</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Scotophaeus relegatus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma capensis</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma fusca</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trephopoda kannemeyeri</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907*	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus bicavus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus capensis</i> Purcell, 1907	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes albanicus</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes caldarius</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes humilis</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
HERSILIIDAE	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ceratinopsis dippenaari</i> Jocqué, 1984	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Prinerigone vagans</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
LIOCRANIDAE	<i>Rhaeboctesis matroosbergensis</i> Tucker, 1920	5	DD	SAE
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa faberrima</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Arctosa promontorii</i> (Purcell, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna unicolor</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa manubriata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1903	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Pterartoria caldaria</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Pterartoria polysticta</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
	<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
MIGIDAE	<i>Moggridgea terricola</i> Simon, 1903	5	VU	SAE
MIMETIDAE	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
OECOBIIDAE	<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
PHOLCIDAE	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Lamaika distincta</i> Griswold, 1990	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cispius</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
	<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)*	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euprosthénopsis lamorali</i> Blandin, 1977	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Nilus curtus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1876	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euophrys leipoldti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Habrocestum luculentum</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus insperatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus pratti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> (Dufour, 1831)	0	LC	C
	<i>Mexcala rufa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Myrmarachne leleupi</i> Wanless, 1978	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pseudicius africanus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rumburak bellus</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala hirsuta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes flagellata</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer, 1837	0	LC	C
	<i>Scytodes testudo</i> Purcell, 1904	5	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE	<i>Anyphops capensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops hessei</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops lesserti</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Anyphops purcelli</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	4	DD	SAE
SICARIIDAE	<i>Hexophthalma spatulatus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE
	<i>Palystes castaneus</i> (Latreille, 1819)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875*	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes lycosinus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	LC	SAE
STASIMOPIIDAE	<i>Stasimopus brevipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C

	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C
	<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872*	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Harpactira cafreriana</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Harpactira dictator</i> Purcell, 1902	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Harpactirella domicola</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DDT	SAE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euryopsis</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841*	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus indistinctus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion delicatum</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3 (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Theridion</i> sp. 4 (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
THOMISIDAE	<i>Avelis hystriculus</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	5	NT	SAE
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema imitator</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890*	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus havilandi</i> Lawrence, 1942*	3	LC	SAE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afroseto capensis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	5	RARE	SAE
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900*	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Heradida speculigera</i> Jocqué, 1987	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Psammoduon canosum</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
ZOROPSIDAE	<i>Griswoldia robusta</i> (Simon, 1898)	5	LC	SAE

Endemicity (END): (6) only known from the type locality, Bontreboek National Park endemic; (5) endemic to Western Cape Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; WCE, Western Cape endemic.

Grassland spiders of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides the first species list of spiders presently known and protected in the Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State, South Africa. A total of 138 species from 104 genera and 36 families are presently known from the area. The most species-rich families are the Araneidae (21 spp.), Thomisidae (17 spp.) and Salticidae (14 spp.). A large number of the species have been photographed, including their webs. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution is provided. Approximately 5.9 % of the total South African spider fauna is represented on the Estate.

Key words: checklist, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), webs

INTRODUCTION

Grasslands are ancient and date back to well before the break-up of the earth's landmass into continents and oceans. In the Afrotropical Region, true grasslands currently survive only in South Africa, and represent about 16.5% of the total land area. Grasslands are primarily found in the summer rainfall areas, from sea level to altitudes above 3000 m, and cover large parts of the Gauteng, Mpumalanga, Free State, Eastern Cape and North West provinces. The climate typically consists of warm, wet summers followed by cold, dry winters with heavy frosts. Frost, fire and grazing are some of the factors that prevent the spread of shrubs and trees. It is a unique ecosystem with a rich and often highly specialized fauna. The vegetation is dominated by grass species, with many forbs also present. Grasslands burn regularly, often every year, and the plants and animals are often adapted to survive fires (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida surveys are underway in grassland areas, with the main aim of documenting the diversity of the biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). The first checklist on the spiders of the Grassland Biome was published by Haddad *et al.* (2013), listing 58 families and 792 described species. A book on the Grassland species followed soon after (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014). There are many unique grass-dwelling spiders, with special adaptations in body form, colour, and web and retreat construction, such as retreats or egg sacs constructed in inflorescences, or as a framework for web construction. Many species have special adaptations in shape and colour that make them cryptic on grass. Many have become nocturnal to escape the high daytime temperatures in the summer and to utilize the large quantity of insects available at night. By preying on insects and even other arachnids, spiders are an important component in grassland food webs.

South Africa's spider species are not evenly distributed across the country and the highest diversity is recorded in the provinces of Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal (Foord *et al.* 2020). Many of the spider surveys of the Free State focused on the ground- (Lotz *et al.* 1991; Haddad *et al.* 2015; Haddad & Butler 2018; Neethling & Haddad 2019), termitaria- (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002, 2006), foliage- (Haddad 2005; Fourie *et al.* 2013; Neethling & Haddad 2013), tussock- (Luwes & Haddad 2020; Haddad *et al.* 2021) and leaf litter-dwelling (Butler & Haddad 2011; Haddad *et al.* 2019) spider assemblages, all conducted in the central Free State.

The work we report on here was not conceived as a scientific study as such, but are the result of many observations and a photographic survey undertaken regularly over a 14-year period in a grassland fragment at Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the eastern Free State Province, South Africa (Fig. 1). No quantitative methods were used and the main focus was hand searching and observations on the grass inhabitants (Fig. 2).

METHODS

Study area: The survey was carried out in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) that is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands, some 14 km from Clocolan (Fig. 1). The MCE (28°48'S, 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and it is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop), sanctuary and nature reserve. The estate is on average 1700 m above sea level, with an annual rainfall of 720 mm.

A 230-million-year-old koppie "Spitskop" is an integral part of the estate and is home to a rich natural heritage of Flora and Fauna (Figs 3 & 4). The second author (Allen Jones) and Jenny Lotter have been the owners of MCE since 2002.

FIGURE 1: Map of South Africa, showing the location of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate.

FIGURE 2: Survey at Mpetsane Conservancy Estate in 2007.

The grasslands have been re-wilded, wild flowers and plants have returned, with an abundance of insects and spiders. In 2005, the owners contacted the members of SANSa and initiated a survey to determine the arachnid diversity of the MCE, resulting in several reports in previous SANSa Newsletters.

Study method: The majority of observations were made by the second author (AJ). While staying on the reserve he was regularly walked in the field to photograph spiders and make observations. In March 2007, members of the Pretoria SANSa survey team undertook a collecting trip to MCE to collect arachnids (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2007). They were joined by Charles Haddad of the University of the Free State and Leon Lotz of the National Museum, Bloemfontein (Jones 2007).

Photography: As part of SANSa a Virtual Museum was developed where photographs could be submitted by the public as an additional method to plot the distribution of spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2012). More than 2000 photographs of the arachnids of MCE were taken over the years. This include a large series of web images (see Figs 5 & 6).

Specimens: Sampled arachnids were identified by the first (ASD) and third authors (CH). Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. Material is also housed in the Arachnida Unit at the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

FIGURE 3: The 230-million-year-old koppie "Spitskop" at the Mpetsane Estate.

FIGURE 4: The grassland area at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate.

Endemicity value: The endemicity value was provided for each species (Appendix 1) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognized: 6 = MCE, known only from type locality (Mpetsane Conservation Estate); 5 = FSE, known only from the Free State Province but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE known from two adjoining provinces (South African Endemic); 3 = South Africa, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining (SAE); 2 = STHE, known from southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider project, the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DDT (data deficient for taxonomic reasons) or DD when there is a lack of distribution data. Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Family diversity: A total of 138 species from 103 genera and 36 families have been recorded from MCE to date, with the Araneidae (21 spp.), Thomisidae (17 spp.) and Salticidae (14 sp.) the most species-rich families (Table 1; Appendix 1). The dominant grass-dwelling families apparently vary geographically and according to grassland type. In the drier grasslands of the central Free State, the numerically dominant grass-dwelling families include Thomisidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae and Araneidae, although the abundance of each may vary between different grassland types (Haddad 2005; Fourie *et al.* 2013).

A large number of web-dwellers are listed, including several ground web-dwellers such as *Benoitia ocellata* of the Agelenidae (Figs 5a,f), *Chiasmopes namaquensis* (Roewer, 1955), *Euprosthops australis* Simon, 1898 and *Euprosthopsis pulchella* (Pocock, 1902) of the Pisauridae, and *Hippasa australis* Lawrence, 1927 (Lycosidae). Numerous plant web-dwellers are listed, such as the Araneidae (Fig. 5c, d, g, j), Dictynidae (Fig. 5e) and Eresidae (*Stegodyphus dumicola* Pocock, 1898).

The Araneidae (21 spp.) and Tetragnathidae (3 spp.) species are all orb-web dwellers, except *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) that make a reduced orb-web. Their large webs are visible early in the morning while still covered with dew (Figs 5b, g, j). Several of the araneid species were also recorded from the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.* 2013), but there were several species such as the three *Argiope* spp., *Argiope aurocineta* Pocock, 1898, *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) (Jones 2012), *Argiope lobata* (Pallas, 1772), *Cyrtophora citricola* (Forsskål, 1775), and the two golden orb-web spiders, *Trichonephila fenestrata* Thorell, 1859 and *T. senegalensis annulata* (Thorell, 1859) Figs 5c, d, g), that were not previously recorded from surveys.

At MCE the populations of *Argiope australis*, *A. lobata*, *Cyrtophora citricola* (Fig. 5d) and *Trichonephila fenestrata* (Fig. 5c) sometimes built up to very high numbers during the year (Jones 2012a, b).

Several new species and new records have been reported from MCE. Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones (2008) reported on the first record of *Cyrtarachne ixoides* (Simon, 1870) (Araneidae) from South Africa. More recently, a small ground-dwelling spider was described, *Eleleis haddadi* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020, with MCE as the type locality. From *Eucalyptus* leaf litter another new species *Capobula montana* Haddad, Jin, Platnick & Booyesen, 2021 was described, but it is widespread in the Eastern Cape, Free State and Lesotho.

Species conservation and endemism: Of the 138 species sampled, only *Eleleis haddadi* is a MCE endemic. Two trapdoor spiders are Free State endemics, *Ancylotrypa dreyeri* (Hewitt, 1915) and *Stasimopus minor* Hewitt, 1915, as is the daddy long-legs spider *Quamtana lotzi* Huber, 2003 (Pholcidae). These four Free State endemic species are of particular concern, especially *Eleleis haddadi*, which is only known from one specimen from MCE.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Mpetsane Conservation Estate, with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S).

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	3
Araneidae	14	21	Phyxelididae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	4
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Salticidae	11	14
Clubionidae	1	3	Scytodidae	1	1
Corinnidae	4	5	Segestriidae	1	2
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	1	2
Eresidae	2	4	Sparassidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	6	6	Stasimopidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	2	3
Hersiliidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	1	1	Theridiidae	6	9
Lycosidae	10	12	Thomisidae	12	17
Mimetidae	1	1	Trachelidae	4	5
Oxyopidae	2	4	Trochanteridae	1	1
Palpimanidae	1	1	Uloboridae	1	1
Philodromidae	3	5	Zodariidae	2	2

Five species could not be determined and were not evaluated, while four species were Data Deficient due to their unresolved taxonomy (Appendix 1). The majority of species (130) have a wide distribution and are considered to be of Least Concern.

CONCLUSION

This inventory adds some species to the Free State species list and provides some information on their behavior, especially for the web builders.

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FIGURE 5: Web images from Mpetsane Conservancy Estate. (A-B) Sheet and funnel-webs of the ground dwelling spiders including species of Agelenidae, Lycosidae and Pisauridae; (C) Dense orb-webs of the Araneidae species; (D) Adapted orb-webs of the Araneidae; (E) Retreat-webs of Dictynidae; (F) Funnel-web of Agelenidae; (G) Orb-webs Araneidae and Tetragnathidae; (H-I) Sheet-webs of Pisauridae and Lycosidae; (J) Orb-webs (Photos: A. Jones).

FIGURE 6: Common spiders of Mpetsane Conservation Estate. (A) *Gephyrota glauca* (Jézéquel, 1966) (Philodromidae); (B) *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pavesi, 1883) (Pisauridae); (C) *Oxyopes bothai* Lessert, 1915 (Oxyopidae); (D) *Camaricus nigrotesselatus* Simon, 1895 (Thomisidae); (E) *Tibellus minor* Lessert, 1919 (Philodromidae); (F) *Runcinia erythrina* Jézéquel, 1964 (Thomisidae); (G) *Euprosthops australis* Simon, 1898 (Pisauridae); (H) *Clubiona* sp. (Clubionidae); (I) *Baryphas ahenus* Simon, 1902 (Salticidae); (J) *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) (Araneidae); (K) *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875 (Thomisidae); (L) *Archaeodictyna conducta* (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876) (Dictynidae) (Photos: A. Jones).

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APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate, listing their endemcity (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution (DIST).

SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
1. Family Agelenidae			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
2. Family Araneidae			
<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
<i>Argiope aurocineta</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyrtarachne ixoides</i> (Simon, 1870)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Larinioides</i> sp. 1		NE	
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
3. Family Caponiidae			
<i>Caponia hastifera</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
4. Family Cheiracanthiidae			
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
5. Family Clubionidae			
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Clubiona</i> sp. 3		NE	
6. Family Corinnidae			
<i>Cambalida dippenarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE
<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE
<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE
7. Family Cyrtachenidae			
<i>Ancylotrypa dreyeri</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	5	DDT	SAE
8. Family Dictynidae			
<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
9. Family Eresidae			
<i>Dresserus kannemeyeri</i> Tucker, 1920	4	LC	SAE
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
10. Family Gnaphosidae			
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Eleleis haddadi</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020	6	DDT	MCE

APPENDIX 2: - continued.

<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
11. Family Hahniidae			
<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
12. Family Linyphiidae			
<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C
13. Family Lycosidae			
<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Amblyothele albocincta</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
14. Family Mimetidae			
<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
15. Family Oxyopidae			
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
16. Family Palpimanidae			
<i>Palpimanus</i> sp. 1		NE	
17. Family Philodromidae			
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
18. Family Pholcidae			
<i>Quamtana lotzi</i> Huber, 2003	5	DD	FSE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
19. Family Phyxelididae			
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
20. Family Pisauridae			
<i>Chiasmopes namaquensis</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Euprosthénops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
21. Family Salticidae			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE

APPENDIX 2: - continued.

<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heliophanus prozysniskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
<i>Psenec dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
22. Family Scytodidae			
<i>Scytodes drakensbergensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	4	LC	SAE
23. Family Segestriidae			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
24. Family Selenopidae			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
25. Family Sicariidae			
<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981	4	LC	SAE
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
26. Family Sparassidae			
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
27. Family Stasimopidae			
<i>Stasimopus minor</i> Hewitt, 1915	5	DDT	FSE
28. Family Tetragnathidae			
<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872	0	LC	C
29. Family Theraphosidae			
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
30. Family Theridiidae			
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 2		NE	
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3		NE	
<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE
29. Family Thomisidae			
<i>Camaricus nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Firmicus bipunctatus</i> Caporiacco, 1941	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses gibbus</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984	3	LC	SAE
<i>Oxytate concolor</i> (Caporiacco, 1947)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE

APPENDIX 2: - continued.

<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisops sulcatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
30. Family Trachelidae			
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Capobula montana</i> Haddad, Jin, Platnick & Booyesen, 2021	2	LC	STHE
<i>Poachelas striatus</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	3	LC	SAE
<i>Thysanina absolve</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	5	LC	FSE
<i>Thysanina transversa</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	3	LC	SAE
31. Family Trochanteriidae			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE
32. Family Uloboridae			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
33. Family Zodariidae			
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE

Endemicity (END): (6) known only from the type locality, Mpetsane Conservation Estate; (5) endemic to the Free State Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; FSE, Free State endemic.

Notes on the orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT

Notes on the rare orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) are provided. The species is known from East, West, Central and South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed and live photographs are provided, with notes on their lifestyle.

Key words: Afrotropical, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, SANSa Virtual Museum, savanna, webs

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Afracantha* is a monotypic African genus described by Dahl (1914). The type species, *Afracantha camerunensis*, was described from Cameroon by Thorell (1899) as *Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis*. The species is recorded from seven African countries (World Spider Catalog 2021). They are known as the Spiny-Backed Orb-Web Spiders.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012). Several sets of photographs of *Afracantha camerunensis* were received from the public. During surveys, spiders were sampled and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council—Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Afracantha camerunensis (Thorell, 1899)

Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis Thorell, 1899: 65 (Df).

Gasteracantha batesi Pocock, 1900: 858, pl. 56, fig. 10 (Df); Dahl, 1914: 252, fig. 7 (f).

Isoxya camerunensis Benoit, 1962: 25, fig. 18

Afracantha camerunensis Emerit, 1974: 29 (Tf from *Isoxya*).

Description: Total length: female 9 mm. Male unknown. Colour: carapace dark orange to black, with white setae on each side; abdomen light orange with black patches and some anterior median white pigment spots dorsally; legs pale brown, bearing clusters of white setae. Carapace broad, with slight indentation between the cephalic and thoracic region; hump is present behind the eye region; lateral eyes close together, situated on carapace border but widely spaced from median eyes; posterior median eyes slightly wider apart

than anterior median eyes. Sternum with posterior tip extending between coxae of leg IV. Abdomen high in lateral view, hard and covered with scattered brown hairs; viewed dorsally, anterior edge rounded, bearing sigilla; two prominent tubercles with sharp tips present posterolaterally and another pair on posterior edge (Fig. 1). Legs short and arranged around the carapace.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ghana, Swaziland, Botswana, Zambia, South Africa.

FIGURE 1: *Afracantha camerunensis* female, dorsal view, from Kloof (Photo: D. Pelsers).

FIGURE 2: *Afracantha camerunensis* female, from Kloof, dorsal view (A) and lateral view (B) (Photo: D. Pelsler).

LIFESTYLE

On two occasions the web of *A. camerunensis* was spotted in KwaZulu-Natal. The first was in a camp-site in an open area of mown grassland dotted with *Vachellia* trees in the Umgeni Valley (Heron 2017). The spider was suspended in a vertically oriented colourless orb-web with a diameter of about 20 cm and supported by a long bridge line about half a metre wide below an overhead branch of *Vachellia nilotica*.

The orb-web was situated about 2.0 m from the ground. The second web was photographed at Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 3).

HABITAT

The species is known to occur in the shrub and tree layer in the Savanna and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes (Foord *et al.* 2011).

FIGURE 3: *Afracantha camerunensis* female in a dense orb-web at Kloof (Photo: D. Pelsler).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (FIG. 4)

Eastern Cape: Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Hell's Gate) (-28.00, 32.48); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24) (Haddad *et al.* 2006); Ophathe Nature Reserve (-28.52, 31.66) (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-25.73, 32.00); Umgeni Valley (-29.47, 30.20). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003).

FIGURE 4: Map showing the distribution of *Afracantha camerunensis* in South Africa

CONSERVATION

An African endemic species previously recorded from six African countries. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces and conserved in five protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

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